

Enhancing mechanical properties and moisture durability of flax fibre composites by plasma treatments

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Introduction

Why natural fibres?

- Renewability
- Biodegradability
- Low carbon footprint
- Lightweight
- Good specific strength and modulus
- Excellent thermal and acoustic insulation
- Safe and non-toxic

[1-2]

[1] Jauhari N, et al. Natural Fibre Reinforced Composite Laminates - A Review. Materials Today: Proceedings (2015).

[2] Pickering KL, et al. A review of recent developments in natural fibre composites and their mechanical performance. Compos Part A (2016)

Introduction

Challenges and issues of natural fibres

- Variance in dimension and geometry
- Processing temperature restrictions
- Low flame and thermal resistance
- Poor interfacial adhesion 😞
- High moisture absorption 😞

Surface treatments

Chemical treatments

- Alkali
- Acetylation
- Silane
- Peroxide treatment
- Benzoylation
- ...

Physical treatments

- Corona
- Plasma
- Ultraviolet
- Heat treatments
- ...

Introduction

What is plasma?

[1]

Plasma treatments for natural fibres

- Cleaning
- Etching
- Functionalization
- Polymerization

Material systems

Flax fibres

(a)

(b)

(c)

Unidirectional flax fibres (non-twisted and non-crimp) at different scales: (a) fabrics, (b) zoom-in local fabrics, and (c) technical fibres

Matrix materials	Melting point	Polarity	Affinity with flax fibres	Activation gas	Polymerization monomer + carrier gas
Polyoxymethylene (POM)	165 °C	Slightly polar	Modest	Air	3-aminopropyltriethoxysilane (APTES) + 95.5 % N ₂ /4.5% O ₂
Polypropylene (PP)	165 °C	Non-polar	Poor	Air/ N ₂	Hexamethyldisiloxane (HMDSO) + 95.5 % N ₂ /4.5% O ₂ or pure N ₂

Plasma treatments

➤ Atmospheric pressure plasma treatment

Illustration of plasma activation and plasma polymerization using a dielectric barrier discharge reactor PlasmaZone®

Material system 1: flax/polyoxymethylene (POM)

Surface morphology analysis

- Compared to the untreated fibres, plasma-activated fibres exhibit grooves and crevices on their surface, indicating surface etching.
- In the case of plasma-coated fibres, a thin coating layer is observed, and the surface appears smoother, suggesting that the coating may partially fill in or mask the surface roughness.

Wetting analysis and fibre pull-out test

Contact angle measurement

Fibre pull-out test

- Theoretical work of adhesion (W_a) indicates the physical adhesion for the samples treated by both plasma activation and coating is improved, but the interfacial shear strength (IFSS) shows that only sample treated by plasma activation is enhanced.

Flexural strength and modulus

- Plasma activation outperforms plasma polymerization in enhancing flexural properties, consistent with the trend observed in interfacial shear strength.
- While the flexural moduli of the composites increased after plasma treatments, their flexural strengths were reduced.

Impregnated fibre bundle test (IFBT)

Back-calculation of the fibre properties

- The moduli of the plasma-treated fibres showed no significant change; however, noticeable reductions in tensile strength were observed, indicating fibre degradation induced by the plasma treatments.

[1] Bensadoun F, et al. Impregnated fibre bundle test for natural fibres used in composites. *Journal of Reinforced Plastics and Composites* (2015)

Material system 2: flax/polypropylene (PP)

Optimization of plasma treatment parameters- exposure time (P) and discharge power (W)

- Air-based plasma activation showed no improvement in the flexural strength across all parameter combinations tested. N₂-based plasma activation with 15P and 300 W efficiently increased the flexural strength in the composites.

Surface chemistry

Plasma treatments for flax/PP

- N₂ plasma activation- paN₂
- Plasma polymerization using HMDSO with carrier gas of pure N₂ - ppHMDSO (100% N₂)
- Plasma polymerization using HMDSO with carrier gas of 95.5 % N₂/4.5% O₂ - ppHMDSO (4.5% O₂)

Surface chemical composition of untreated and plasma-treated flax fibres

Samples	C 1s (%)	O 1s (%)	N 1s (%)	Si 2p (%)	O/C	Si/C	Si/O
Untreated	85.1 ± 1.1	12.8 ± 0.6	1.6 ± 0.2	0.8 ± 0.1	0.15	0.01	0.06
paN ₂	76.0 ± 4.3	19.6 ± 3.6	3.1 ± 0.5	0.7 ± 0.3	0.26	0.01	0.04
ppHMDSO (100% N ₂)	47.3 ± 2.3	27.0 ± 2.3	3.7 ± 0.2	22.0 ± 0.5	0.57	0.47	0.81
ppHMDSO (4.5% O ₂)	29.7 ± 1.9	44.1 ± 2.0	0.5 ± 0.2	25.7 ± 1.4	1.48	0.86	0.58

Contributions of functional groups (%) on the surface of flax fibres

Samples	C-(C,H) (285.0 eV)	C-O/C-N (286.5 eV)	C=O/O-C-O (287.9 eV)	O=C-O (289.2 eV)	Si 4+ (103.6)	Si 3+ (102.8 eV)	Si2+ (102.1 eV)
Untreated	60.6 ± 1.2	18.2 ± 0.9	4.8 ± 0.6	1.5 ± 0.2	-	-	-
paN ₂	64.1 ± 4.6	21.0 ± 2.8	9.8 ± 1.2	5.2 ± 0.6	-	-	-
ppHMDSO (100% N ₂)	-	-	-	-	14.7 ± 2.8	57.4 ± 2.4	28.0 ± 0.4
ppHMDSO (4.5% O ₂)	-	-	-	-	61.0 ± 2.1	38.3 ± 2.4	0.7 ± 0.4

Silica-like

PDMS-like

Moisture absorption test

$$M_t = \frac{W_t - W_0}{W_0} \times 100\% \quad W_0: \text{the weight of the dry sample}; W_t: \text{the weight at equilibrium}$$

- The N₂ plasma-treated composites showed increased moisture content compared to untreated sample, probably due to the higher surface energy.
- The HMDSO coating using 4.5% O₂ as a carrier gas, effectively reduced moisture absorption at 85% RH. This is likely because the silica-like coating acts as a barrier (denser molecular structure [1]), mitigating the moisture diffusion.

[1] Walker M, et al. Investigations of plasma polymerized barrier films on polymeric materials. Surface and Coatings Technology (2005).

Flexural properties

- The highest flexural strength and modulus were observed in HMDSO-coated composites using 100% N₂ as carrier gas, demonstrating an enhancement of 24% and 33%, respectively, compared to those of untreated composites at the standard indoor humidity.
- The lower flexural properties of the composites at 85% RH is attributed to the additional failure on the compression side.

Conclusions

1. The efficiency of plasma treatments largely depends on the careful selection of treatment parameters, which should be guided by a solid understanding of the surface chemistry and physical properties of the materials involved. For polar polymers (POM), enhancing surface energy can significantly improve the interface properties. However, in the case of hydrophobic polymers such as polypropylene (PP), chemical compatibility in terms of hydrophilicity appears to play a more critical role.
2. It is essential to consider potential fibre degradation caused by plasma exposure. Achieving optimal composite performance requires a delicate balance between enhancing fibre-matrix adhesion and preserving fibre strength.
3. Effective plasma polymerization aimed at improving interfacial adhesion often contributes to better moisture resistance. Nevertheless, the barrier property (permeability) of the deposited coating is also important and should be considered in the overall design of the surface treatment.

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